

Application of Differential Electrolytic Potentiometry to the Titration of Iodate Ion with Ferrous Ion in Different Acid Solutions

N. B. MAZUMDAR, K. CHATTERJEE and S. N. DAS

Physical Chemistry Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Patna University, Patna 800 005

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Differential electrolytic potentiometry of the reaction between potassium iodate in hydrochloric, sulphuric and phosphoric acid solutions and ferrous ion is reported in this communication. Accurate titrations are possible in the three acid solutions of moderate concentrations, but the mechanism of reduction of IO_3^- by Fe^{2+} appear to be different in each. In hydrochloric acid solutions, the differential titration curves show one single peak corresponding to the formation of ICl_3 . In sulphuric and phosphoric acid solutions the number of peaks in the titration curve increase to two and three respectively, indicating intermediate formation of I^{2+} species in both, which is subsequently reduced to iodine. In phosphoric acid, iodine is further reduced and the third peak indicates the reduction of iodate ion ultimately to iodide ion. An additional peak appears when the titrations in sulphuric and phosphoric acid solutions are carried out in presence of potassium chloride. This peak at 4 moles of titrant corresponds to the formation of ICl during the course of reduction. Optimum conditions for the titrations are discussed.

DIFFERENTIAL electrolytic potentiometry affords a method of investigating both total and partial reaction. Bishop^{1,2} has examined in detail the applicability of this method to redox titrimetry and he, as well as Reilley, Cooke and Furman³, carried out a number of titrations in this context including those involving the reduction of Ce^{4+} , $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ and MnO_4^- by Fe^{2+} . Classical zero-current potentiometric titration of IO_3^- by Fe^{2+} was found to be feasible by the authors⁴ in high acid concentrations only, who also found that reduction of IO_3^- in hydrochloric acid solutions resulted in the formation of ICl_3 and then ICl . Some of the advantages of differential electrolytic potentiometry being high rates of potential equilibration and accurate location of a succession of end points, the method was applied in the present work in an attempt to understand the mechanism of reduction of iodate ion and to see whether titrations with Fe^{2+} in lower acid concentrations are possible. Accordingly the lower limit of hydrochloric, sulphuric and phosphoric acid solutions in which titrations were done was 1N to 2N, below which titrations were not feasible.

Experimental

The apparatus used were essentially those described by Van Name and Fenwick⁵. A pair of identical platinum wires, 5mm long (at times wires of greater length had to be used) and 0.25mm diameter served as the stationary indicator electrodes, the differential potential, E_{Δ} , across which was measured by a high input resistance potentiometer (Cambridge bench type pH meter). The electrodes were connected in series with ballast resistors (half-watt carbon radio resistors) of 20 to 100 megohms. Current source was a battery of dry cells of 100 volts and a minute ($1\mu\text{A}$ to $5\mu\text{A}$) heavily stabilised polarising current was thus continuously passed through the pair of indicator electrodes immersed in the titration solution. As low stirring rate affects the differential

potential and a constant potential is reached only when the rate is sufficiently high,⁶ the solution was stirred at a constant rate at just below cavitation speed by using a magnetic (at times a mechanical) stirrer. Stable potential readings were rapidly attained in most cases. The titration cell contained 150 ml. of 0.001 M KIO_3 , in different acid solutions (of varying strengths) as supporting electrolytes. The titrant solution (for titrations in sulphuric acid solutions), 0.1M $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot (\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in H_2SO_4 , stored in nitrogen atmosphere and periodically standardised⁷, was added from a semi-microburette. For titrations in hydrochloric acid and phosphoric acid, the titrant solutions were: FeCl_2 in HCl and $\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)_2$ in H_3PO_4 , the two ferrous salts being prepared by dissolving pure iron wire in hydrochloric acid⁸ and phosphoric acid⁹ respectively. Reagents used were all of AnalaR grade.

Differential titration curves were obtained by plotting the differential potential, E_{Δ} , against the volume of titrant (expressed as moles of Fe^{2+} per mole IO_3^-) added. In plotting each successive curve the titrant volume zero was progressively shifted along the X-axis but the same voltage scale was used for all the curves. Titrations were carried out mostly at room temperature (ca. 25°) but in sulphuric and phosphoric acid of moderate concentrations (below 10 N), the solutions titrated were heated to 60°, for obtaining smooth and reproducible titration curves and for rendering the electrode reactions more reversible. The shape and form of the curves was found also to depend both on the concentration of the acid solution and on the magnitude of the current density on the electrodes. Optimum conditions were established by performing titrations under varying conditions. In hydrochloric acid solutions sharp and reproducible peaks were obtained when the electrolysis current was $1\mu\text{A}$ to $2\mu\text{A}$, the size of the wire electrodes were as long as 4.5cm and their distance apart also was 4.5cm. In sulphuric and phosphoric

acid solutions the electrolysis current density on the indicator electrodes were much higher : the electrolysis current being $5\mu\text{A}$, the length of the wire electrodes 5mm which were 1.5cm apart.

Results

(i) *Titration in hydrochloric acid solutions :*
 Titrations were performed in hydrochloric acid solutions of concentrations varying from 9N to 1N-typical

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

titration curves [(A)2N HCl, (B)5N HCl, (C)7N HCl] are given in Figure 1. A single sharp peak in the differential curve is obtained in each case at exactly 2 moles of Fe^{2+} per mole IO_3^- provided the acid concentration is below 6N. At higher acid concentrations the peak requires more than 2 moles Fe^{2+} , e. g. in (C) the peak is at 2.4 moles.

(ii) *Titration in sulphuric acid solutions :* In these titrations sulphuric acid concentration was varied from 2N to 16N. Figure 2 contains some [(A)4N H_2SO_4 , (B)10N H_2SO_4 , (C)16N H_2SO_4] of the typical titration curves. Two sharp and reproducible peaks, a small one succeeded by a larger one, is obtained in each of the differential curves : at 2 moles and 5 moles of Fe^{2+} per mole IO_3^- respectively. Some of these titrations were repeated in presence of chloride ions, which resulted in the appearance of an additional peak [e.g. Figures 4: (A)6N H_2SO_4 and 0.04M KCl] at 4 moles of Fe^{2+} per mole of IO_3^- .

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

(iii) *Titrations in phosphoric acid solutions*: Figure 3 contains some of the typical curves of titrations in presence of phosphoric acid [(A)4*N* H₃PO₄, (B)8*N* H₃PO₄, (C)14*N* H₃PO₄] of concentrations varying from 2*N* to 20*N*. An initial small peak at 2moles of Fe²⁺ is succeeded in each case by a larger one at 5moles of Fe²⁺ per mole IO₃⁻. Beyond the second peak there is a vertical fall in the differential curve which then rises steeply showing a break (at about 6 moles in 14*N* H₃PO₄). This last break tends to disappear with H₃PO₄ concentration increasing beyond 14*N*, when the nature of the curves also change. Thus in 16*N* H₃PO₄ solution there is only one peak at 5moles of Fe²⁺ which is not very sharp. In presence of chloride ions an additional peak [e.g. figure 4 (B)6*N* H₃PO₄ and 0.1*M* KCl] at 4moles of Fe²⁺ per mole IO₃⁻ appears.

(iv) *Forms of titration curves*: Titrations in hydrochloric acid solutions yield symmetrical differential curves with sharp positive going peaks showing steep rise and fall (peak height 200mV) from near zero bases. In sulphuric acid solutions an initial fall in the differential curve is followed by a small but well defined peak. This is succeeded by a second peak larger than the first, beyond which the curve registers a steep vertical fall of about 400mV. In presence of potassium chloride the form of the curves is changed, and an additional peak appears in between the two peaks beyond which the curve falls steeply and then rises again—after which the final peak appears as before.

Initial portions of titration curves of titrations performed in phosphoric acid solutions resemble those from sulphuric acid solutions. The steeply falling portion of the curves beyond the second peak (peak height about 350mV), however, starts rising again and finally exhibits a break after which it tends to become flat. When chloride ion is present, the differential curve shows an additional break in between the two initial peaks.

Discussion

In hydrochloric acid solutions of concentrations between 2*N* to 6*N* the single peak in the differential curve at 2 moles of Fe²⁺ per mole of IO₃⁻ corresponds with the reduction of IO₃⁻ completely to ICl₃: IO₃⁻ + 3Cl⁻ + 6H⁺ + 2Fe²⁺ = ICl₃ + 3H₂O + 2Fe³⁺ (1). The reduction process does not seem to proceed further under the conditions in which the titrations are performed. Peaks requiring more than 2 moles Fe²⁺ at higher acid concentrations perhaps indicate partial reduction of ICl₃ to ICl or I₂. Iodine trichloride had been isolated and its thermodynamic properties have been measured.¹⁰ Its formation during the reduction of IO₃⁻ in hydrochloric acid solutions has previously been noted⁴. Equation (1) involving formation of ICl₃, accords well with stoichiometric requirement of the titration curves but the formation of ICl₃ in preference to ICl is still to be explained.

Both in sulphuric and phosphoric acid solutions (concentrations between 4*N* to 16*N*) two peaks at

2 moles and 5 moles of Fe²⁺ per mole of IO₃⁻ corresponds with stepwise reduction of IO₃⁻, first to I³⁺ and then finally to I₂. Thus in sulphuric acid the reduction of iodate to iodine may involve intermediate formation of iodine sulphate:

Similarly in phosphoric acid solutions intermediate formation of iodine phosphate is indicated:

At the second peak at 5 moles of Fe²⁺ therefore the net reaction in both acids amount to:

Equations (3) and (4) involve SO₄²⁻ and PO₄³⁻ ions which in high acid concentrations would not perhaps exist in appreciable amounts. These equations therefore may be considered to represent the overall reaction corresponding to stoichiometric requirements. In this context it may be mentioned that oxidation of iodine leads to the formation of salt like compounds of tripositive iodine,^{11,12} including the sulphate I₂(SO₄)₃, and the phosphate, IPO₄. The assumption therefore of intermediate formation of these compounds during the reduction of iodate (initially formed I₂ being oxidized by IO₃⁻) seems justified.

An interesting feature of titrations in these two acids in presence of chloride ions is the appearance of an additional peak at 4 moles of Fe²⁺ per mole IO₃⁻ which could correspond to initial reduction in presence of Cl⁻, either of I₂(SO₄)₃ or IPO₄ to ICl.

Reduction of IO₃⁻ to ICl in strong HCl solutions was noted by Andrews¹³. However, we failed to get a peak corresponding to its formation in titrations in HCl solutions. In strong H₂SO₄ and H₃PO₄ on the other hand a relatively small concentration of Cl⁻ seems to lead to its formation according to the following net reaction:

Another salient feature is that titration in phosphoric acid solutions yield curves with a further peak at about 6 moles of Fe^{2+} per mole of IO_3^- . It is possible that, in presence of PO_4^{3-} ions, iodine is further reduced by Fe^{2+} to I^- - this would correspond with :

The overall reaction therefore would be

It may be noted in this context that Bonner and Romeyn¹⁴ have shown that the reaction (10) goes to completion in the presence of phosphate (even though the reaction is slow), probably due to the formation of a weak electrolyte of composition varying from FePO_4 to $\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)_3$. The peak corresponding to reaction (10) is not reproducible probably because the reaction is slow.

Forms of differential curves throw some light on the reversibility of the species being electrolysed at the two polarised electrodes^{3,6}. As steep rise and fall would indicate the existence of reversibly electrolysable species, we conclude from an examination of titration curves in Figures 1 to 4 that the titrant systems (i. e., $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ system) is reversible in HCl and H_2SO_4 solutions but is only partly reversible in phosphoric acid solutions. The titrate system, $\text{IO}_3^-/\text{I}^{3+}$, appears to be reversible in hydrochloric acid but only partly reversible in sulphuric acid and phosphoric acid solutions.

The nature of the other relevant peaks would also suggest that the various systems involved in the reduction process (comprising I^{3+} , I^+ , I^0 and I^-), are none of them wholly reversible.

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